

Medicinal Unmet Health Needs: Role of Pharmacology

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Abstract

Health, an important resource and top most priority of every living creature, is affected by number of factors both intrinsic and extrinsic. Derangement in health often follows various therapeutic intervention to restore function of living organism. Every nation directs its utmost efforts to provide adequate healthcare facility to its citizen; but in almost every instance, there exist gap between health care demands and supply. Medicine forms the core of most of therapy and the science dealing with drugs is popularly known as pharmacology. India, despite known as hub of traditional medicine, most of Indian population do not get all the medicines when required. This article aims to make society aware of role of pharmaceutical industry and to create space for pharmacologists and the pharmaceutical organizations to listen to, learn from, and connect with, people with a diverse range of expertise and experience to develop a novel drug for the betterment of society.

Introduction

Health, as per World Health Organization, is "a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease and infirmity". Health being the top most priority of every living creature, is affected by number of factors. In the context of human being, health is constantly affected by a variety of agents present in the surrounding environment, which is ultimately linked to nation economy as huge expenditure as percentage of the gross domestic product are invested in health sector in most countries (Adegoke and Wright, 2013). Performing healthful activities, such as regular physical exercise and adequate sleep, and by reducing or avoiding unhealthful activities, such as smoking or excessive stress, will keep human being healthy (CDC, 2022). Whenever any kind of

derangement occurs in health, we follow various therapeutic strategies, which create health needs. Every nation directs its utmost efforts to provide adequate healthcare facility to its citizen; but in almost every instance, there exist gap between health care demands and supply, popularly known as “health inequalities (Who, 2018).” Health inequalities are unfair and avoidable differences in health across the population, and between different groups within society (Who, 2018). In Indian context, wealth, education, and occupation inequalities are the major determinants of health inequality. In addition, religion, caste, and tribal affiliations are important contextual indicators of inequity that influence health and health care in India (Selvaraj et al., 2022). The COVID-19 pandemic has further strengthened the existing inequalities.

Amongst the various therapeutic strategies, medicines or drugs mostly forms the core of therapy. Drugs or medicines ranges from anti allergic, antipyretic medicines to anti-cancer drugs depending on the requirement. Indian traditional system of medicine being known for world's oldest medical systems was based upon six systems, Ayurveda, Unani, Siddha, Homeopathy, Yoga and Naturopathy (Ravishankar and Shukla, 2007). Recognized for its potential, recently, the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Government of India signed an agreement to establish the WHO Global Centre for Traditional Medicine (WHO-GCTM) at Jamnagar, Gujarat (Who.int). Since past, the use of herbal and animal extracts and minerals has been with us for thousands of years as a very early form of therapeutics. At the core of medicine, there lies the pharmacology i.e. science of drugs. Often confused with pharmacy, pharmacology is a separate discipline in the health sciences and deals with science of how drugs act on biological systems and how the body responds to the drug. The study of pharmacology encompasses the sources, chemical properties, biological effects, and therapeutic uses of drugs. Pharmacy, on the other hand uses the knowledge derived from pharmacology to achieve optimal therapeutic outcomes through the appropriate preparation and dispensing of medicines. Pharmacology integrates the knowledge of many disciplines, including medicine, pharmacy, dentistry, nursing, and veterinary medicine (ASPET, 2021). This integrative nature allows pharmacology to make unique and significant contributions to human and animal health.

In the context of medicines or drugs, unmet health needs mean shortage of medicine to a population and is wide spread in public health centres across states in India in both humans (Kotwani et al., 2007), (Cameron et al., 2009) and animals, with COVID-19 pandemic further increasing the gap (FDA, 2019). Increased demand, unavailability of active pharmaceutical agent, supply chain disruption, and decrease in manufacturing are the causes of shortage of medicines. In addition, lack of incentives for manufacturers to produce less profitable drugs; lack of appreciation of market and reward manufacturers for “mature quality systems” that focus on continuous improvement and early detection of supply chain issues; and Logistical and regulatory challenges make it difficult for the market to recover from a disruption are also the other

reasons responsible for shortage of medicine ((FDA, 2019). This article aims to make society aware of role of pharmaceutical industry and to create space for pharmacologists and the pharmaceutical organizations to listen to, learn from, and connect with, people with a diverse range of expertise and experience to develop a novel drug for the betterment of society.

Role of Pharmacology in Meeting Health Needs

Pharmacology helps people around the world to live healthier lives for longer with the help of drugs (www.bps.ac.uk). It does so by producing drugs against various ailments ranging from allergy, simple fever, to a complicated conditions like cancer, rheumatoid arthritis, degenerative diseases, etc. With the help of pharmacology and by employing multidisciplinary approach, pharmacologists had produced drugs ranging from anti-inflammatory drugs, antibiotics, to various anti-viral and antineoplastic therapies. The examples of drugs from different classes includes- cetirizine, paracetamol, aspirin, rifampicin, xylazine, fentanyl, penicillin, isoflurane, remdesivir, amantadine, zidovudine, ketoconazole etc (WHO, 2021). In line with this, antiviral drug like Remdesivir and monoclonal antibody baricitinib were approved and were used for the treatment of much dreadly COVID-19 in adults and pediatric patients (Yasuda et al., 2022). In order to discover a new medicine or drug, pharmacologists basically work across the life cycle of drugs and therapeutics to understand how they work, develop better medicines, and ultimately to make a positive impact on health outcomes. In this way, pharmacology and pharmacologists helps to address challenges pertaining to health by (www.bps.ac.uk)-

- ✓ Discovering and developing new medicines to tackle diseases
- ✓ Identifying new treatments when old one's stop being effective
- ✓ Exploring how we can best use the medicines we already have
- ✓ Tackling antibiotic resistance
- ✓ Studying ageing to help us all live healthier lives for longer
- ✓ Researching to make sure medicines are effective for everyone
- ✓ Helping to make sure that everyone is prescribed the right medicines for them

Conclusion and future perspectives

Although efforts are already on the way to integrate biology/physiology, chemical biology/biological chemistry, pharmacogenetics, experimental medicine, systems biology departments and use of modern technologies in education and research, an important consideration should be given to how we deploy research, development, and care to where they are needed most - particularly considering limited resources and global health challenges. In this aspect, we need to identify potential gaps in unmet health needs and how pharmacology and allied disciplines can help us to solve them. At the same time

strengthening our basic education, application of basic principles, need driven approach, and more inclination towards practical aspect can help to achieve desired targets effectively. Creating zeal amongst the students since their childhood about science, and its magical power can help to boost overall aspect of human well-being. Regular follow up with the help of various initiatives through meetings, journals, policy work, and industrial academic collaboration can certainly make an impact. All this will spark new ideas for future research and collaboration of various government and non-governmental agencies is of utmost importance in this regard.

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